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Data management plan (DMP)

Machine-actionable data descriptions for Austria's digital landscape model

EOSCSecretariat.eu

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1.0	13/05/2023	Transferred text from internal document
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List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management
DLM	Digitales Landschaftsmodell
BEV	Bundesamt für Eich- und Vermessungswesen
INSPIRE	Infrastructure for spatial information in Europe

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Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- TU Wien Policy for Research Data Management: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Policy%20for%20Research%20Data%20Management.pdf>
- TU Wien Code of Conduct – Rules to Ensure Good Scientific Practice: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Code%20of%20Conduct%20E2%80%93%20Rules%20to%20Ensure%20Good%20Scientific%20Practice.pdf>
- Directives and Regulations of the TU Wien Rectorate: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/directives-regulations/>
- TU Wien Data Protection: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/data-protection-at-tu-wien>
- European Commission's document on Ethics and Data Protection: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/5_h2020_ethics_and_data_protection.pdf
- Other (e.g. from a project partner)

1. Data description

1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced

Produced datasets

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	d1mdesc	Structured text	json	500 MB	No
P2	d1mdesc.git	Source Code	git	10 MB	No

Reused datasets

dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	INSPIRE theme register	http://inspire.ec.europa.eu/theme	CC-BY-4.0	no
R2	Digitales Landschaftsmodell - Verkehr Stichtag 25.01.2023	10.48677/ed8c11ce-c7e4-4d04-bf33-fcaabbaf1158	CC-BY-4.0	no
R3	Digitales Landschaftsmodell - Gewässer Stichtag 25.01.2023	10.48677/33ce91a5-08bc-42f3-aa10-f5bfa1d2a5b7	CC-BY-4.0	no
R4	Digitales Landschaftsmodell - Gebietsnutzung Stichtag 25.01.2023	10.48677/cc3b5a81-8234-4315-9634-c84dd9786549	CC-BY-4.0	no
R5	Digitales Landschaftsmodell - Bodenbedeckung Stichtag 25.01.2023	10.48677/d8e8e465-e365-43fe-b31d-bdaa9fd1f4ff	CC-BY-4.0	no
R6	Digitales Landschaftsmodell - Bauwerke Stichtag 25.01.2023	10.48677/0e36cab1-698a-42a7-b72d-9631d2d7ad28	CC-BY-4.0	no

R7	Digitales Landschaftsmodell - Bauten Stichtag 25.01.2023	10.48677/3d0f31d2-9811-4bf3-b3dd-9f22df7caaa5	CC-BY-4.0	no
R8	Digitales Landschaftsmodell - Geographische Namen INSPIRE Stichtag 25.01.2023	10.48677/458469ad-b310-445a-ac64-d6e5b2a7db65	CC-BY-4.0	no

1b Data generation and reuse

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The software will generate a machine actionable data structure from the associated data descriptions, the data sets themselves will be used solely to validate and enrich.

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

File names are identical to the source files, only the file extension changes. Version control is automated with Git.

We will be using the following domain specific metadata standards: json-schema.org. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description, or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

A far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

A separate repository is provided for PDF parsing, facilitating reuse and validation for other purposes. This makes the documentation of pdf specific steps clearer.

2b Data quality control

The following data quality checks will be done: Validation if the created data description is inconsistent with the data sets will assure that there are no obvious mistakes. In addition, a random manual check is carried out.

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the project manager. Only the source code will be backed up because the data generation is fully automated. For this purpose, GitHub is sufficient, though for publication the data will be transferred to a different repository.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	writing	no access
P2	writing	writing	reading only
R1	reading only	reading only	reading only
R2	reading only	reading only	reading only
R3	reading only	reading only	reading only
R4	reading only	reading only	reading only
R5	reading only	reading only	reading only
R6	reading only	reading only	reading only
R7	reading only	reading only	reading only
R8	reading only	reading only	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and ownership

Legal restrictions on how data is processed and shared are specified in the Specified in the doi reference. The restrictions relate to datasets R2 (Digitales Landschaftsmodell - Verkehr Stichtag 25.01.2023), R3 (Digitales Landschaftsmodell - Gewässer Stichtag 25.01.2023), R4 (Digitales Landschaftsmodell - Gebietsnutzung Stichtag 25.01.2023), R5 (Digitales Landschaftsmodell - Bodenbedeckung Stichtag 25.01.2023), R6 (Digitales Landschaftsmodell - Bauwerke Stichtag 25.01.2023), R7 (Digitales Landschaftsmodell - Bauten Stichtag 25.01.2023), and R8 (Digitales Landschaftsmodell - Geographische Namen INSPIRE Stichtag 25.01.2023). The legal restrictions are based on the following: CC-BY-4.0 Copyright disclaimer

Bundesamt für Eich- und Vermessungswesen has rights to the produced data and controls access.

4c Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Restricted	Embargo without specified reason	2023-03-15	zenodo.org	10.5281/zenodo.7935103	CC BY 4.0
P2	Restricted	Embargo without specified reason	2023-03-15	zenodo.org	10.5281/zenodo.7935103	UNLICENSED

Methods or software needed to access and use data: No, the JSON format is human readable, and most program languages have native parsing support.

Description of protocol to access restricted data: The data set can be generated with the publicly available source code.

5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P2	Github Archive	10 years	Officers of local/national governments

Overview of (unpublished) data that will be deleted:

dataset ID	kind/name of data	date of deletion	reason for deletion	responsible person

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

The PI will direct the data management process overall, with the research assistants responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained. The lead country researchers will be responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

Cost name	Cost type	Description	Unit	Value
Estimated total costs				0

Additional description (if required):